

The Ultimate Survivors, bacterial resistance by selection and resistance induction to antibiotics, common biocides and also commonly used drugs not usually associated with antimicrobial activity

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Abstract:

Background:

Antibiotics, and biocide antiseptic disinfectants e.g. Triclosan and Chlorhexidine are all used for their antimicrobial properties. Other commonly used drugs like Ibuprofen and Fluoxetine are routinely used by many in the industrialised world but are generally not perceived to be associated with antimicrobial activity

Aims:

To investigate the effects of biocides and two commonly used oral, non-antimicrobially associated drugs on the growth and susceptibilities of common pathogenic bacteria.

Materials and methods:

Staphylococcus aureus, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were each plated onto different media containing Triclosan, Chlorhexidine, Ibuprofen, or Fluoxetine at different measured concentrations to investigate their antimicrobial properties. Susceptibility testing was performed on colonies grown on each media to measure its resistance levels.

Results:

Five of the 64 bacterial tests showed increased resistance to antibiotics after 72hrs incubation when compared to values obtained after 24hrs. In particular, Triclosan and Fluoxetine each showed inducibility of resistance in *K. pneumoniae* at sub-lethal concentrations.

Conclusions:

More research is needed into the potential antimicrobial resistance-inducing properties of commonly used biocides as well as other commonly used drugs which are not usually associated with antimicrobial resistance but may in fact also be contributing to the development of antimicrobial drug resistance in common bacterial strains, as well as microbiome perturbation.

Introduction:

Since the discovery of penicillin in 1928, and the beginning of its mass routine use in the 1940s, bacteria have constantly been under ongoing survival pressure from many antibiotics and disinfectants. As time went on, more antimicrobial substances were found to help us lead the fight against infection; and in doing so, numerous resistant strains of bacteria have emerged to the extent of threatening much of the basis of medicine in the industrialised world. Mechanisms of resistance to antimicrobial drugs have been broadly categorized into 2 groups: modifying the affinity of the antimicrobial target, or lowering the active concentration of antimicrobial in the cell. In regards to

the latter, active efflux, or active excretion of the antimicrobial drug, has been categorized as a notable mechanism of resistance in bacterial cells² as well as in human eukaryotic cells, leading to the ineffectiveness of some chemotherapy treatments. It is important to note that some efflux pumps have been found to be broad-action, reducing intracellular concentrations of antibiotics and biocides alike.¹³

To combat these emerging resistant pathogens researchers have turned to non-antibiotic means to help fight the rising tide of resistance. Biocides, such as Triclosan and Chlorhexidine, have been a mainstay in hospital and healthcare facilities for years, being used as scrubs and generalized antiseptic washes to reduce bacterial loads for nearly two decades.⁷

Triclosan has been a staple ingredient in soaps, cosmetics, and toothpaste, being found in over 70% of commercial soaps in 2001.¹⁹ Until recently Triclosan has been one of the most frequently used antiseptic washes in hospitals with concentrations varying from 0.1% to 1.0%. After being thoroughly examined by the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) in 2010 and later years, it was found to be an inducer of antibacterial resistance as well as a causative agent of endocrine imbalances through the production of chloroform when mixed with chlorinated water.¹⁰ Since the FDA received no evidence from any Triclosan soap manufacturers on request of any beneficial effects of this antibacterial soap in the domestic situation, only harms, the Triclosan additive has now been banned for domestic soap sales in the USA.

Chlorhexidine has been a popular biocide since the 1950's¹⁷ and with its low mammalian toxicity and broad-spectrum antimicrobial effect, it has become a common biocide used in hospitals around the world. Use of it has been noted to not only increase resistance to itself but also to induce multiple antibiotic resistances in some strains of bacteria including *S. aureus* via multidrug efflux mechanisms²¹ – ironically where it has been used for attempting skin decolonisation of MRSA. With all these side-effects of biocides being researched, they have come under increased scrutiny and are increasingly being regarded like antibiotics in regards to their use and increasing microbial resistance potential.¹¹ For both biocides, the main action of antimicrobial activity is cell membrane destruction.

Since its creation in 1969, Ibuprofen has been a mainstay in most households, accounting for 50% of non-steroidal anti-inflammatories in the UK during 1986³ and since then, this number has only increased worldwide due to its easy availability in pharmacies and supermarkets. Recent studies have shown Ibuprofen to have some degree of antimicrobial effect. Methods of action vary and range from inhibition of growth to metabolic interference.²⁹

Prozac, whose main metabolite is Fluoxetine, was the most widely prescribed antidepressant on the market as of 2004.²⁴ A study performed by Munoz-Bellido et al. showed antidepressants, including Fluoxetine, to have an antimicrobial effect against bacterial strains. Strong antimicrobial activity was shown against gram-positive bacteria, namely *Staphylococcus spp.* and *Enterococcus spp.* Less pronounced activity was shown against potentially toxigenic *Enterobacteriaceae spp.* In human eukaryotic cells, these drugs are known to have an inhibitory effect on efflux pumps, though there is little research available into its effect on efflux mechanisms in bacterial cells.¹⁵

The purpose of the current study was to compare the antimicrobial activity of different drugs and their ability to induce antibacterial resistance, with a focus on potential active efflux mechanisms.

Method and Materials:

Materials for the experiment:

Three of the four bacterial strains used were reference strains obtained from ESR (the Institute of Environmental Science and Research, Porirua, New Zealand) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC27853, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC25923 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC25922 with the other strain *Klebsiella pneumoniae* being isolated from a clinical sample. Each strain had been deemed fully susceptible according to Eucast guidelines for the antibiotic disks used.¹² Cefaclor was the only antibiotic disc which used zone sizes from CLSI guidelines. The drugs used (Chlorhexidine, Triclosan, Ibuprofen, Prozac (Fluoxetine)) were obtained from CDC Pharmaceuticals Ltd (Christchurch, New Zealand). Mueller Hinton agar plates, Nutrient agar plates, and antibiotics discs used for susceptibilities were purchased from Fort Richard Laboratories (Auckland, New Zealand). The following discs used were manufactured by BBL: Ampicillin (10µg), Ciprofloxacin (5µg), Gentamicin (10µg), Cotrimoxazole (25µg), Cefaclor (30µg), Cefpodoxime (10µg), Ceftazidime (10µg), Clindamycin (2µg), Penicillin (1µg), Tetracycline (30µg), Cefoxitin (30µg), and Erythromycin (15µg).

Dilution, plating of drugs and bacteria:

The drugs were diluted to their respective concentrations with either sterile water (Chlorhexidine and Triclosan) or 100% ethanol (Ibuprofen and Fluoxetine) with final working concentrations being: Chlorhexidine (4%, 2%, 1%, 0.5%), Triclosan (1%, 0.5%, 0.25%, 0.125%), Ibuprofen (50mg/ml, 25mg/ml, 12.5mg/ml, 6.25 mg/ml), and Fluoxetine (20mg/ml, 10mg/ml, 5mg/ml, 2.5mg/ml). 1ml of each solution was spread onto a nutrient agar plate and left to dry. Three plates were plated for each concentration (i.e. Triplicate testing), with each triplicate labelled for a different time point (24hrs, 48hrs, and 72hrs). Four sets of triplicates were plated out for each of the four bacterial species tested. In total 192 plates (64 tests over 3 days) were labeled and spread. When the bacteria were spread (using a swab with 0.5 MacFarland standard turbidity concentration) onto the plates, a crosshatch pattern was used to easily visualize bacterial growth after incubation at 37°C. Each plate was read after 24hrs, with any colonies present after the incubation being streaked onto another plate containing the same concentration as the previous plate. The newly streaked plates were incubated for a subsequent 24hrs. This method was used to easily visualize bacterial growth as it grew on the plates.

Susceptibility testing of organisms:

For each plate with growth, a colony was removed and mixed with sterile saline to a turbidity of 0.5 McFarland standard and a lawn of bacteria was streaked onto a labeled Mueller Hinton plate. The following diffusion discs were used for each bacterial strain as described in Table 1:

Table 1. Antibiotic discs used for susceptibilities

<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
Cefoxitin (30µg)	Ciprofloxacin (5µg)	Ciprofloxacin (5µg)	Ciprofloxacin (5µg)
Penicillin (1µg)	Gentamicin (10µg)	Ampicillin (10µg)	Ampicillin (10µg)
Clindamycin (2µg)	Ceftazidime (10µg)	Cefpodoxime (10µg)	Cefpodoxime (10µg)
Erythromycin (15µg)		Cefaclor (30µg)	Cefaclor (30µg)
Cotrimoxazole (25µg)		Cotrimoxazole (25µg)	Cotrimoxazole (25µg)
Tetracycline (30µg)		Gentamicin (10µg)	Gentamicin (10µg)

Results were read after 24hrs and tabulated.

Testing of temporary resistance induction:

Colonies on the nutrient agar treated with Triclosan 0.5% were inoculated onto untreated nutrient agar, followed by 6hr incubation at 35° 5% CO₂. Susceptibility testing was performed on any colonies present. Those colonies were later inoculated onto untreated nutrient agar for 24hr incubation at 35°C. Susceptibility testing was performed on this growth as well. This method was repeated for each of the different drugs at the varying concentrations.

Results:

Plates were read and recorded using a grading system, with scores ranging from 0 (no growth) then 1 (least growth) increasing to 10 (heavy growth) then confluent growth recorded as TMC (too many to count) as delineated below: 0 (0 colonies), 1 (1-25 colonies), 2 (26-50 colonies), 3 (51-75 colonies), 4 (76-100 colonies), 5 (101-125 colonies), 6 (126-150 colonies), 7 (151-175 colonies), 8 (176-200 colonies), 9 (201-225 colonies), 10 (226-250 colonies), TMC (>250 colonies). The normal therapeutic values for each drug (when acting in the gut or on the skin) are: Chlorhexidine 0.5%, Triclosan 0.25%, Ibuprofen 50mg/ml, 25mg/ml, 12.5mg/ml, and Fluoxetine 5mg/ml, 2.5mg/ml.

Table 2. Day 1, 2, 3 growth of bacterial species against different drugs and concentrations

	Incubation	<i>S. aureus</i>			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			<i>E. coli</i>			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Chlorhexidine	4%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	1%	1	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	3	0	0
	*0.5%	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
Triclosan	1%	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	9	TMTC	TMTC
	0.5%	1	0	0	1	TMTC	TMTC	1	0	0	9	TMTC	TMTC
	*0.25%	0	2	0	1	1	TMTC	1	0	0	TMTC	TMTC	9
	0.125%	1	5	0	1	2	TMTC	1	0	0	TMTC	TMTC	9
Ibuprofen	*50mg/ml	1	0	0	10	TMTC	9	9	6	9	9	9	10
	*25 mg/ml	0	0	0	TMTC	TMTC	10	TMTC	9	10	1	6	1
	*12.5 mg/ml	3	0	0	TMTC	TMTC	TMTC	TMTC	9	10	7	7	1
	6.25 mg/ml	9	1	3	TMTC	TMTC	TMTC	TMTC	10	9	2	6	3
Fluoxetine	20 mg/ml	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
	10 mg/ml	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
	*5 mg/ml	0	0	0	4	2	6	1	0	0	1	0	1
	*2.5 mg/ml	0	0	0	TMTC	9	7	0	0	0	1	3	1

*Asterix denotes normal therapeutic concentration

0-10 increasing bacterial growth count up to TMTC

TMTC= Too many to count, confluent growth

Control incubation plates without any drug were all confluent growth TMTC on day 1-3

Over the 3 days:

- the biocide Chlorhexidine showed almost complete sustained inhibition of bacterial growth for each strain tested, as expected
- the biocide Triclosan
 - showed almost no growth at day 1 for *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and complete inhibition of growth after three days
 - *K. pneumoniae* colony counts increased significantly from occasional colonies at day 1 to confluent growth (TMTC) over 3 days at the three $\leq 0.5\%$ concentration levels, showing that this biocide induces microbial resistance to it within this timeframe.
 - *P. aeruginosa* had relatively uninterrupted growth throughout the three days
- The drug Ibuprofen
 - had a sustained marked significant inhibitory effect over all 3 days incubation on the growth of *S. aureus*
 - *E. coli* was confluent growth (TMTC) at day 1, reduced to relatively heavy but not confluent growth on day 2 and 3
 - *P. aeruginosa* was sustainably significantly inhibited over all 3 days at the three concentrations $\leq 25\text{mg/ml}$
 - *K. pneumoniae* was effectively not inhibited over all 3 days
- Fluoxetine had
 - Complete (*S. aureus*) to near-complete (*E. coli*) inhibitory effect on over days 1 and 2, with complete inhibition for both species by day 3
 - *K. pneumoniae* complete inhibition over all 3 days at 10 and 20 mg/ml and significantly reduced growth at 5mg/ml over all 3 days
 - *P. aeruginosa* had marked sustainable inhibition over all 3 days

Antibiotic susceptibilities of the colonies grown on the plates are listed in the appendix. Five susceptibility profiles showed significant decreases in zone sizes i.e. these drugs had induced significant increases in antibiotic resistances, as shown in the tables and graphs below.

Table 3. *K. pneumoniae* susceptibilities

	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>					
	Triclosan 0.5%					
	GM (Gentamicin)	CIP (Ciprofloxacin)	AP (Ampicillin)	CPD (Cefpodoxime)	CFC (Cefaclor)	TS (Cotrimoxazole)
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	23mm	33mm	12mm	33mm	29mm	32mm
48hrs	18mm	20mm	/	22mm	23mm	24mm
72hrs	19mm	22mm	/	23mm	23mm	26mm
6hrs untreated	18mm	26mm	8mm	24mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs untreated	22mm	32mm	11mm	28mm	23mm	29mm

After 72hrs growth on the selected drug concentration, the bacteria were grown on non-inhibitory media to re-assess antibiotic susceptibilities. '/' represents no growth inhibition by antibiotic discs

Figure 1. *K. pneumoniae* treated with Triclosan 0.5% After 24hrs incubation on the modified media, colonies showed increased susceptibility to all antibiotic discs used. 0hrs zone diameters refer to known test zone diameters prior to the test. After 48hrs, there were noticeable decreases in zone sizes. After 72hrs a slight increase occurred in the zone sizes. After 6hrs of growth on unmodified media showed a generalised increased zone size across all susceptibility levels, with 24hrs growth on unmodified media showing the strain returning to its previous susceptibility levels. Zone diameter of 0 denotes no inhibition from the disc.

Table 4. *K. pneumoniae* susceptibilities

	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> Triclosan 0.25%					
	GM (Gentamicin)	CIP (Ciprofloxacin)	AP (Ampicillin)	CPD (Cefpodoxime)	CFC (Cefaclor)	TS (Cotrimoxazole)
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	25mm	29mm	7mm	25mm	26mm	31mm
48hrs	22mm	22mm	/	21mm	22mm	22mm
72hrs	20mm	18mm	/	18mm	21mm	18mm

After 72hrs growth on the selected drug concentration, the bacteria were grown on non-inhibitory media to re-assess antibiotic susceptibilities. '/' represents no growth inhibition by antibiotic discs

Figure 2. *K. pneumoniae* treated with Triclosan 0.25%. After 24hrs incubation on the modified media, colonies showed increased susceptibility to all antibiotic discs used. After 48hrs, there were noticeable decreases in zone sizes. After 72hrs, the increased resistance smaller zone size trend continued. Zone diameter of 0 denotes no inhibition from the disc.

Table 5. *K. pneumoniae* susceptibilities

	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> Triclosan 0.125%					
	GM (Gentamicin)	CIP (Ciprofloxacin)	AP (Ampicillin)	CPD (Cefpodoxime)	CFC (Cefaclor)	TS (Cotrimoxazole)
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	21mm	28mm	10mm	28mm	27mm	29mm
48hrs	18mm	17mm	/	21mm	21mm	16mm
72hrs	19mm	16mm	/	21mm	20mm	16mm

After 72hrs growth on the selected drug concentration, the bacteria were grown on non-inhibitory media to re-assess antibiotic susceptibilities. '/' represents no growth inhibition by antibiotic discs

Figure 3. *K. pneumoniae* treated with Triclosan 0.125% After 24hrs incubation on the modified media, colonies showed increased susceptibility to all antibiotic discs used. 24hrs later, there were noticeable decreases in zone sizes. After 48 and 72hrs, the zone diameters remained approximately constant. Zone diameter of 0 denotes no inhibition from the disc.

Table 6. *K. pneumoniae* susceptibilities

	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> Fluoxetine 5mg/ml					
	GM (Gentamicin)	CIP (Ciprofloxacin)	AP (Ampicillin)	CPD (Cefpodoxime)	CFC (Cefaclor)	TS (Cotrimoxazole)
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	23mm	33mm	/	33mm	28mm	33mm
48hrs	19mm	19mm	/	20mm	21mm	21mm
72hrs	19mm	21mm	/	20mm	22mm	20mm

After 72hrs growth on the selected drug concentration, the bacteria were grown on non-inhibitory media to re-assess antibiotic susceptibilities. '/' represents no growth inhibition by antibiotic discs

Figure 4. *K. pneumoniae* treated with Fluoxetine 5mg/ml After 24hrs incubation on the modified media, colonies showed an increased susceptibility to most of the antibiotic discs used. 24hrs later, there were noticeable decreases in zone sizes. After a further 24hrs, the zone diameters remained fairly consistent. Zone diameter of 0 denotes no inhibition from the disc.

Table 7. *K. pneumoniae* susceptibilities

	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> Fluoxetine 2.5mg/ml					
	GM (Gentamicin)	CIP (Ciprofloxacin)	AP (Ampicillin)	CPD (Cefpodoxime)	CFC (Cefaclor)	TS (Cotrimoxazole)
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	24mm	23mm	/	23mm	24mm	17mm
48hrs	12mm	13mm	/	20mm	23mm	22mm
72hrs	18mm	20mm	/	20mm	21mm	22mm

'/' represents no growth inhibition by antibiotic discs

Figure 5. *K. pneumoniae* treated with Fluoxetine 2.5mg/ml After 24hrs incubation on the modified media, colonies showed increased susceptibility to most of the antibiotic discs used, apart from Cotrimoxazole and Ampicillin. 24hrs later, there were noticeable decreases in some zone sizes, with others increasing. After a further 24hrs, the zone diameters showed an overall decrease from the original diameters. Zone diameter of 0 denotes no inhibition from the disc.

Susceptibility patterns of the above tests show an overall decrease in zone diameter with time post drug challenge which correlates with an increase in MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration) i.e. an increase in antibiotic resistance. When compared with the untreated samples, zone sizes at time 48hrs and 72hrs show a noticeable decrease, easily visualized in Figures 2 & 3. Zone diameters after incubation on chemical-free media (*K. pneumoniae* with Triclosan 5%) for 6hrs and 24hrs showed similar zone diameters to those of the untreated strains, demonstrating a re-lowering of the MIC, i.e. a return to normal antibiotic susceptibility without the ongoing presence of the drugs tested.

Discussion:

Each of the strains of bacterial species tested in this experiment are regular colonizers of the human microbiome, as well as common environmental bacteria.^{4,9} While colonization is asymptomatic, these organisms, under the right conditions, are common pathogens.²² Triclosan and Chlorhexidine are expected to show antimicrobial action against bacteria, but Fluoxetine and Ibuprofen are not generally associated with antimicrobial action, nevertheless they both displayed significant mixed antimicrobial action on the small number of test bacterial species challenged by them at normal gut intake dose levels. It could be assumed that many more of the large number of species comprising our microbiome would also be similarly inhibited.

Five of the 64 drug challenge tests against common microbe pathogens showed susceptibility patterns representative of significantly increased bacterial drug resistance. These bacteria were cultured on media containing sub-lethal and normal therapeutic concentrations of the drugs. Decreased zone diameters from an antibiotic-impregnated disc are reflective of an increased MIC i.e. the more resistant the bacteria are to that drug the higher the concentration (growth nearer to the disk with drug impregnated in it) of drug required to inhibit it. MIC is defined as the minimum inhibitory concentration of antibacterial drug required to inhibit further growth of the organism.¹ MIC zone diameter breakpoints (Susceptible, Resistant) for the organisms used in this test are in accordance with the EUCAST guidelines, and can be found in Appendix B. After 24hrs on the modified nutrient agar, all strains showed increased zone diameters. During this period, the strains showed no immediate signs of selective resistance being present. After a further 24hrs of drug challenge, overall zone diameters started to decrease, indicating some form of resistance being induced. In most cases, this trend continues after a further 24hrs incubation on modified agar. The continued decrease in zone diameter is further representative of MIC increase and increased bacterial resistance.

After the *K. pneumoniae* treated with Triclosan at 0.5% was incubated for 6hrs drug-free, increases in the zone diameter could be seen, showing the resistance was only temporary and while being challenged by the drug. This was further confirmed by the incubation of the same strain on unmodified nutrition agar, with the zone diameters effectively returning to what they were prior to treatment challenge. It is interesting to note that *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* initially grew substantially more in 1% Chlorhexidine than in 0.5% Chlorhexidine, compared to the lack of growth on the *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* plates, using the same drug concentrations. During hand washing, the concentration of the soap and chlorhexidine being used is decreased, but nevertheless residual on the skin unlike alcohol, leading to a more favourable environment for gram-negative proliferation, as the more predominant gram positives (e.g. *Staphylococcus spp.*) are more easily killed at lower concentrations.

There is a fine line of differentiation between selection of a resistant organism in small numbers from a large number present and induction of resistance in an originally totally susceptible group of organisms. If colonies can be seen within the initial zones of inhibition, they are deemed resistant to the selective antibiotic.¹⁶ Since there were no individual colonies found within the initial zones of inhibition, and because the resistance did not appear within 24hrs on known susceptible stock bacterial strains, it could be reasonably assumed that there were no resistant mutations within the original culture tested. It appears that this is consistent with an initial homogenous susceptible bacterial culture, as opposed to heterogeneous,⁶ which is sometimes the case with bacterial growth in nature. This form of later developed resistance appears to be induced, occurring after incubation for an increased period of time on the drug modified media. Genetically, bacterial strains likely harbour the resistant mechanisms used to survive in selective conditions,²⁷ even though they often do not express this resistance phenotypically i.e. this induced resistance ability is not detectable on routine testing methods. The reduction of MIC after 24hrs on unmodified media further supports the idea of induced resistance, also the resistance was temporary as induced efflux resistance often is. Selection for existing phenotypic expressed resistance would harbour the same zone diameter for all susceptibility tests, which was not the case. This method of resistance is consistent with that of efflux pumps, with their often-shorter term expression.⁸ This shorter-term expression does not negate their importance though – while the bacteria is efflux pumping out the drug toxic to it, the bacteria, in turn, remains viable for more generations than it would otherwise be and so has more time to develop chromosomal or plasmid resistance which is maintained longer term. Increased resistance to more than two types of antibiotics, as well as to Triclosan, is characteristic of multidrug efflux pumps.²

In addition to the role of efflux pumps inducing resistance, there is accumulating evidence that multidrug-resistance efflux pumps also have roles in bacterial pathogenicity and it is increasingly being proposed that these pump mechanisms therefore have a greater clinical relevance than just resistance inducing.²⁰

Apart from the demonstrated ability of perceived ‘non-antimicrobial drugs’ to in fact be both antimicrobial as well as induce resistance in some strains, this inhibitory effect of Ibuprofen and Fluoxetine on bacterial growth is a further cause for concern because this unexpected microbial inhibitory effect must then also alter our gut microbiome composition. Recent studies have shown a correlation between gut bacteria and endocrine function/cell signalling in the brain.⁵ With Fluoxetine being one of the most widely used antidepressants at the moment, and Ibuprofen being so easily available, unintentional modification of our gut microbiota can lead to other adverse health outcomes that have an equally if not worse medium to long-term health outcome compared to antibiotic resistance.²⁸ This also raises the question whether Ibuprofen, or other ‘non-antimicrobial drugs’ can somehow be implemented in helping fight some bacterial infections or colonisations, or used in conjunction with standard antibiotics to help fight infection.

As well as the unexpected induction of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains with common ‘non-antibacterial drugs’, transfer of these increasingly resistant organisms between individuals and the environment is a major issue facing modern medicine. Although in this experiment the resistance was only temporary, transfer of resistant organisms is still likely, with new colonization opportunities in new hosts. Once resistant colonization occurs in the new host, removal of resistant organisms is difficult. One study conducted in 1976 showed the swift spread of increasingly antibiotic-resistant bacteria amongst a caged chicken population when only tetracycline was added to the mash of one set of caged birds. Other caged birds in the same barn 60 metres away were not fed any antibiotics.

The bird population which were not fed antibiotics, plus the farming family tending the birds all began carrying the same multiple resistance after weeks to months,¹⁴ demonstrating how easily resistant organisms are transferred within populations of proximity including via the environment.

Conclusion:

Antimicrobial and previously perceived ‘non-antimicrobial’ drugs (Ibuprofen and Fluoxetine) at sub-lethal concentrations demonstrated inhibition of bacterial growth and the ability to induce antibiotic resistance. Each of these effects in itself is a major cause for concern – increasing antibiotic resistance plus changing the composition of our microbiome. Changed microbiome composition is now strongly correlated from thousands of published papers to be increasingly associated with many significant medium to long-term adverse health outcomes. Only two ‘non-antimicrobial drugs’ were tested in this experiment, but they are commonly used by a significant proportion of the population. This has potential major implications for our population health. What other resistances and inhibitions causing microbiome changes are created amongst the very large number of other species in our gut microbiome, including all the other ‘non-antimicrobial’ drugs commonly used. Further study is required to fully understand and appreciate these mechanisms and outcomes. It seems resistance is everywhere, expressed and latent. Inhibition and resistance can both be induced by many common drugs including ‘non-antimicrobials’. We are unknowingly creating many of our own adverse health outcomes.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

Appendix:

Appendix A. Raw data for zone diameters (in mm)
 ‘/’ represents no growth inhibition by antibiotic discs

			<i>E.coli</i> Chlorhexidine 4.0%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	23mm	34mm	21mm	30mm	26mm	29mm
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i> Chlorhexidine 2.0%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i> Chlorhexidine 1.0%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/

			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 0.5%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Triclosan 1.0%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	21mm	35mm	22mm	26mm	24mm	27mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Triclosan 0.5%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	22mm	37mm	26mm	30mm	25mm	30mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Triclosan 0.25%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Triclosan 0.125%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	23mm	35mm	20mm	28mm	24mm	27mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Ibuprofen 50mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	23mm	36mm	20mm	28mm	24mm	27mm
48hrs	21mm	34mm	20mm	26mm	22mm	26mm
72hrs	22mm	32mm	19mm	23mm	21mm	25mm

			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Ibuprofen 25 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	24mm	25mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
48hrs	22mm	36mm	21mm	28mm	24mm	25mm
72hrs	20mm	31mm	18mm	22mm	17mm	22mm
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Ibuprofen 12.5 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	23mm	34mm	21mm	27mm	23mm	29mm
48hrs	23mm	36mm	22mm	28mm	24mm	29mm
72hrs	23mm	21mm	32mm	20mm	24mm	20mm
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Ibuprofen 6.25 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	24mm	35mm	21mm	27mm	22mm	27mm
48hrs	24mm	37mm	22mm	29mm	25mm	26mm
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Fluoxetine 20 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Fluoxetine 10 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>E.coli</i>			
			Fluoxetine 5 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/

			<i>E. coli</i>			
			Fluoxetine 2.5 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	22mm	31mm	21mm	27mm	24mm	27mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	21mm	30mm	12mm	23mm	20mm	24mm
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 4%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 2%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 1%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 0.5%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Triclosan 1%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/

			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Triclosan 0.5%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	23mm	27mm	24mm	25mm	26mm	26mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Triclosan 0.25%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Triclosan 0.125%			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	25mm	27mm	26mm	26mm	27mm	25mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Ibuprofen 50 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Ibuprofen 25 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Ibuprofen 12.5 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26	25mm
24hrs	27mm	32mm	29mm	28mm	33mm	29mm
48hrs	24mm	31mm	26mm	24mm	25mm	24mm
72hrs						

			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Ibuprofen 6.25 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	20mm	28mm	22mm	25mm	29mm	22mm
48hrs	24mm	32mm	27mm	30mm	26mm	25mm
72hrs	20mm	26mm	23mm	24mm	30mm	22mm
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Fluoxetine 20 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Fluoxetine 10 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Fluoxetine 5 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>S. aureus</i>			
			Fluoxetine 2.5 mg/ml			
	E	TS	T	FOX	PG	CD
0hrs	24mm	25mm	26mm	27mm	26mm	25mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 4%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	26mm	30mm	23mm	29mm	30mm	34mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/

			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 2%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 1%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 0.5%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Triclosan 1%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	22mm	30mm	10mm	29mm	28mm	31mm
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Triclosan 0.5%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	23mm	33mm	12mm	33mm	29mm	32mm
48hrs	18mm	20mm	/	22mm	23mm	24mm
72hrs	19mm	22mm	/	23mm	23mm	26mm
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Triclosan 0.25%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	25mm	29mm	7mm	25mm	26mm	31mm
48hrs	22mm	22mm	/	21mm	22mm	22mm
72hrs	20mm	18mm	/	18mm	21mm	18mm

			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Triclosan 0.125%			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	21mm	28mm	10mm	28mm	27mm	29mm
48hrs	18mm	17mm	/	21mm	21mm	16mm
72hrs	19mm	16mm	/	21mm	20mm	16mm
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Ibuprofen 50 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	22mm	31mm	8mm	30mm	29mm	28mm
48hrs	21mm	25mm	/	24mm	22mm	25mm
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Ibuprofen 25 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	21mm	26mm	/	26mm	26mm	28mm
48hrs	20mm	26mm	/	24mm	22mm	25mm
72hrs	19mm	25mm	/	25mm	23mm	25mm
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Ibuprofen 12.5 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	20mm	30mm	/	26mm	26mm	28mm
48hrs	19mm	24mm	/	22mm	20mm	23mm
72hrs	18mm	23mm	/	21mm	22mm	22mm
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Ibuprofen 6.25 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	20mm	30mm	/	29mm	27mm	30mm
48hrs	18mm	26mm	/	19mm	22mm	23mm
72hrs	18mm	19mm	/	21mm	22mm	22mm
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Fluoxetine 20 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/

			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Fluoxetine 10 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
48hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
72hrs	/	/	/	/	/	/
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Fluoxetine 5 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	23mm	33mm	/	33mm	28mm	33mm
48hrs	19mm	19mm	/	20mm	21mm	21mm
72hrs	19mm	21mm	/	20mm	22mm	20mm
			<i>K. pneumoniae</i>			
			Fluoxetine 2.5 mg/ml			
	GM	CIP	AP	CPD	CFC	TS
0hrs	21mm	28mm	9mm	27mm	26mm	28mm
24hrs	24mm	23mm	/	23mm	24mm	17mm
48hrs	12mm	13mm	/	20mm	23mm	22mm
72hrs	18mm	20mm	/	20mm	21mm	22mm
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 4%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	20mm	26mm	30mm			
48hrs	/	/	/			
72hrs	/	/	/			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 2%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	21mm	25mm	25mm			
48hrs	/	/	/			
72hrs	/	/	/			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 1%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	30mm	19mm	28mm			
48hrs	/	/	/			
72hrs	/	/	/			

			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Chlorhexidine 0.5%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	23mm	24mm	28mm			
48hrs	19mm	24mm	30mm			
72hrs						
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Triclosan 1%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	16mm	16mm	28mm			
48hrs	15mm	/	24mm			
72hrs	18mm	23mm	27mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Triclosan 0.5%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	16mm	18mm	26mm			
48hrs	17mm	18mm	27mm			
72hrs	17mm	22mm	27mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Triclosan 0.25%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	15mm	14mm	25mm			
48hrs	11mm	11mm	25mm			
72hrs	18mm	21mm	26mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Triclosan 0.125%			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	15mm	18mm	24mm			
48hrs	10mm	22mm	20mm			
72hrs	19mm	20mm	25mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Ibuprofen 50 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	18mm	23mm	28mm			
48hrs	19mm	21mm	28mm			
72hrs	15mm	19mm	21mm			

			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Ibuprofen 25 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	22mm	22mm	28mm			
48hrs	17mm	18mm	27mm			
72hrs	17mm	24mm	29mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Ibuprofen 12.5 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	16mm	19mm	27mm			
48hrs	16mm	19mm	27mm			
72hrs	20mm	27mm	31mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Ibuprofen 6.25 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	15mm	18mm	26mm			
48hrs	19mm	23mm	30mm			
72hrs	19mm	22mm	27mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Fluoxetine 20 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	/	/	/			
48hrs	/	/	/			
72hrs	/	/	/			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Fluoxetine 10 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	18mm	25mm	34mm			
48hrs	/	/	/			
72hrs	20mm	25mm	31mm			
			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Fluoxetine 5 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	20mm	23mm	31mm			
48hrs	/	/	/			
72hrs	19mm	23mm	28mm			

			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
			Fluoxetine 2.5 mg/ml			
	GM	CAZ	CIP			
0hrs	17mm	23mm	26mm			
24hrs	17mm	19mm	28mm			
48hrs	18mm	24mm	29mm			
72hrs	19mm	25mm	27mm			

Appendix B. zone sizes of antibiotic discs for susceptibility and resistance

		S	R
Coli	AP	14mm	14mm
	CPD	21mm	21mm
	CFC	18mm	15mm
	TS	18mm	15mm
	GM	17mm	14mm
	CIP	26mm	24mm
Staph	PG	26mm	26mm
	E	21mm	18mm
	T	22mm	19mm
	TS	17mm	14mm
	FOX	22mm	22mm
	CD	22mm	19mm
Pseudo	GM	15mm	15mm
	CIP	26mm	26mm
	CAZ	17mm	17mm

AP=Ampicillin
 CPD=Cefpodoxime
 CFC=Cefaclor
 TS=Cotrimoxazole
 GM=Gentamicin
 CIP=Ciprofloxacin
 PG=Penicillin
 E=Erythromycin
 T=Tetracycline
 FOX=Cefoxitin
 CD=Clindamycin
 CAZ=Ceftazidime

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